

FRACTURE OF CRACK DIVIDER Al/Al LAMINATES

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The crack divider fracture characteristics of totally metallic Al/Al laminates were evaluated. These laminates potentially offer greater fracture and fatigue resistance than conventionally machined, forged, or rolled monolithic metal. Additionally, since these materials are totally metallic, they possess higher service temperatures and are more useful in adverse environments than competitive adhesively bonded metal laminates. Six Al/Al laminate panels of approximately 12.7 mm (0.50 in.) thickness were fabricated using diffusion, explosive, and roll bonding procedures. Specific alloy systems investigated included: diffusion bonded and roll bonded 7475 Al/1100 Al and explosive bonded and roll bonded 7075 Al/7072 Al. A typical laminate consisted of five 2.3 mm (0.090 in.) 7475 Al primary layers interleaved with four 0.13 mm (0.005 in.) 1100 Al secondary layers. It was found that all laminates exhibited substantially higher critical fracture toughness than corresponding baseline, monolithic plate alloys. For example, the Al/Al laminates possessed average toughness values that ranged from 33% to 56% higher than those values for monolithic 7075 Al and 7475 Al plates. The toughnesses of the laminates were almost identical to the toughnesses of the single layer 7075 Al or 7475 Al sheets of which these laminates were composed. Scanning electron fractography, optical metallography, and electron probe micro-analysis were used to evaluate laminate fabrication methods and failure modes. Criteria were outlined for efficient metal/metal laminate design for achieving highly damage tolerant structural materials.

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Introduction

Metal laminates are laminar composite materials which typically consist of thin metal sheets bonded together by a lower strength, secondary material (e.g., epoxy). These laminates are attractive as structural elements because they potentially offer greater reliability, increased life expectancy, and lower cost than conventionally forged and machined metal components. In particular, the high fracture and fatigue resistance of these materials have been the subjects of numerous investigations (1-12). These studies have included evaluations of both metal/adhesive and metal/metal laminate configurations, with the majority of this research being directed toward adhesively bonded metal laminates because of the possible cost savings associated with these materials. However, metal/adhesive laminates see limited application in primary structures, because of uncertainties regarding their use in the presence of hostile environments (e.g., salt water) and at elevated temperatures. Thus, totally metallic laminates are of interest for structures operating under these more severe service conditions.

In spite of the previous studies that have been conducted on both metal/adhesive and metal/metal laminates, insufficient data regarding material, configurational, and processing variables are available for efficient structural design using metal/metal laminates. The present study is directed toward evaluating the effects of these various parameters on the fracture toughness of Al/Al laminates. Six different laminate configurations were fabricated and characterized: diffusion bonded and roll bonded 7475 Al/1100 Al laminates and roll bonded and explosive bonded 7075 Al/7072 Al laminates. The metallurgical structures, tensile properties, and crack divider fracture toughness behavior of these laminates were documented, as well as those of baseline monolithic 7475 and 7075 Al sheet and plate. Specific factors addressed included: (1) comparison of laminate properties with baseline monolithic material, (2) evaluation of effect of laminate fabrication method on properties, (3) determination of the relative properties of 7475 and 7075 Al based laminates, and (4) examination of the effect of secondary metal thickness on laminate behavior.

Materials and Test Methods

Materials Selections

The proper selection of primary and secondary laminae materials and thicknesses is an essential feature of an experimental investigation of metal/metal laminates. From previous laminate materials investigations (4, 5, 7, 9) it has been noted that the principal factors which affect the fracture resistance of a laminate are: (1) primary metal properties (strength, toughness, etc.), (2) primary metal lamina thickness, (3) secondary metal properties (strength, ductility), (4) secondary metal thickness, and (5) primary metal/secondary metal bonding characteristics. In the present investigation only the 7075 and 7475 aluminum alloys were used as primary metals. The selections of these alloys were based mainly on fracture toughness vs. thickness characteristics and strength. The primary lamina thickness for each laminate system was selected to be approximately 2.3 mm (0.090 in.), since the fracture toughness of both 7075 and 7475 Al reaches a maximum near this thickness for the high strength temper conditions (-T76, -T6).

The secondary metal is important principally because of its effect on bondplane strength, and therefore on the tendency of the primary laminae to fail in a plane stress manner. Failure of the primary laminae under plane stress conditions is considered necessary to achieve maximum fracture

toughness in laminated panels. For all three processing methods used in laminate preparation, a soft interleaf metal was employed as the secondary or bonding metal. 1100 Al was used as the interleaf metal in all diffusion bonded panels and in one roll bonded panel. 7072 Al was used as the secondary metal in the explosive bonded panel and in one roll bonded panel. The thickness of interleaf metal was varied from 0.05mm (0.002 in.) to 0.25mm (0.010 in.) to evaluate the effect of thickness on laminate properties.

Laminate Selection and Fabrication

Six laminate configurations were fabricated by diffusion bonding, roll bonding, and explosive bonding processes, as outlined in Table I. All laminates consisted of five primary Al alloy layers interleaved with four layers of interleaf metal. Specific details regarding laminate fabrication procedures and laminate configurations are described below.

Diffusion Bonded Laminates. The three diffusion bonded laminate panels were fabricated by DWA Composite Specialties, Inc. These panels consisted of primary layers of 2.3mm (0.090 in.) thick 7475-T761 Al sheet interleaved with four layers of 1100 Al. The only differences among the three panels were the 1100 Al interleaf thicknesses. These panels were processed under vacuum for 1/2 hr at 477°C (890°F) at 20.7 MPa (3000 psi) pressure. The area of each laminate was approximately 406mm x 711mm (16 in. x 28 in.). Panel thicknesses were 11.7mm (0.46 in.), 11.9mm (0.47 in.) and 12.4mm (0.49 in.). Subsequent to fabrication test specimens were heat treated to the -T7651 temper according to the Alcoa 467 Process for 7475 Al sheet material.

Roll Bonded Laminates. The two roll bonded laminate panels were fabricated and heat treated by Alcoa Technical Center. One laminate configuration (RA1) was composed of 7075 Al sheet interleaved with 7072 Al foil, while the other laminate (RA4) consisted of 7475 Al sheet interleaved with 1100 Al foil. The primary metal layers were nominally 2.3mm (0.090 in.) thick and the interleaf foils were 0.13mm (0.005 in.) thick. Total size of laminate RA1 was

Table I. Laminate Panels Investigated

Bonding Process	Primary Metal	Secondary Metal
Diffusion	2.3mm 7475 Al	0.05mm 1100 Al
		0.13mm 1100 Al
		0.25mm 1100 Al
Roll	2.3mm 7475 Al	0.13mm 1100 Al
	2.3mm 7075 Al	0.13mm 7072 Al
Explosive	2.4mm 7075 Al	0.13mm 7072 Al

11.9mm x 305mm x 1370mm (0.47 in. x 12 in. x 54 in.). Total size of laminate RA4 was 11.9mm x 305mm x 1120mm (0.47 in. x 12 in. x 44 in.). Each laminate panel was fabricated by initially processing three subpanels and warm rolling these three subpanels into the final configuration. After roll bonding the panels to final dimensions the laminates were heat treated to give -T7651 properties to the primary metal phase (7075 or 7475).

Explosive Bonded Laminate Panel. The explosive bonded 7075 Al/7072 Al laminate panel EAl was prepared by Battelle Columbus Laboratories. This laminate was fabricated from five layers of 2.5mm (0.099 in.) 7075-T6 Al clad Al sheet. Thus, the as-bonded laminate consisted of 2.4mm (0.095 in.) 7075 Al interleaved with 0.13mm (0.005 in.) 7072 Al. Total area of the explosive bonded laminate was approximately 12.4mm x 279mm x 381mm (0.49 in. x 11 in. x 15 in.). Subsequent to fabrication the laminate was tempered to give -T76 tensile properties to the 7075 Al.

Mechanical Testing

Room temperature tensile tests were performed in triplicate on all laminate panels and baseline monolithic sheet and plate alloys. These tests were run at 1.27mm/min (0.05 in./min), using 50.8mm (2.00 in.) gage length specimens for all materials except explosive bonded panel EAl. For this material 25.4mm (1.00 in.) gage length specimens were used.

Fracture toughness tests were conducted with single-edge-notched (SEN) and compact tension (CT) specimens of crack divider, L-T orientation. The SEN specimens were 38.1mm x 203mm (1.50 in. x 8.00 in.) in size, while the CT specimens were 61.0mm x 63.5mm (2.40 in. x 2.50 in.) in size. Testing was performed in a manner recommended by ASTM E 399 and the Damage Tolerant Design Handbook (13, 14). Crack lengths were measured by means of a clip gage and an appropriate compliance calibration. These tests were run in triplicate at room temperature on closed-loop servohydraulic test systems. Fracture toughness values determined from compact tension specimen tests were calculated from the stress-intensity expression given in ASTM E 399 (13). Toughness values determined from single-edge-notched specimen tests were calculated from the stress-intensity relation given in Reference (15). The following fracture toughness parameters were calculated: conditional fracture toughness (K_Q), evaluated by the 5% secant method; apparent fracture toughness (K_{app}), evaluated using maximum failure load and the original crack length; and critical fracture toughness (K_{IC}), evaluated using maximum failure load and the crack length at failure.

Results and Discussion

Properties of Baseline Aluminum Alloys

For each of the six laminates evaluated in this study, comparative monolithic plate and single layer sheet material was characterized. For example, the approximately 11.9mm (0.47 in.) thick diffusion bonded laminates, composed of five primary layers of 2.3mm (0.090 in.) 7475 Al sheet, were compared with the sheet metal and with monolithic 7475 plate of 11.9mm (0.47 in.) thickness. Baseline materials evaluated included 2.3mm (0.090 in.) 7475-T761 Al and 7075-T76 Al sheet, 12.7mm (0.500 in.) 7075-T7651 Al plate, and 13.2mm (0.520 in.) 7475-T7651 Al plate. Tensile properties of these materials are given in Table Al in the Appendix. The fracture properties are shown in Table II. As will

be discussed later, apparent and critical fracture toughness were found to be the best measures of laminate panel fracture toughness; therefore, only these parameters have been tabulated. From the data in Table II, it can be seen that 7475 Al has substantially higher fracture toughness than 7075 Al in both sheet and plate form. This observation has been made previously (16-18). The significantly higher fracture toughness that 7475 Al possesses over the 7075 alloy is the principal reason for the present widespread interest in this alloy. Alcoa has attributed the high toughness of this alloy to close chemical composition control and to its Process 467 for heat treatment.

Laminate Microstructures

Prior to sectioning and machining the laminate panels for test specimens, each panel was nondestructively inspected for unbonded areas using ultrasonic C-scan. It was found that all diffusion bonded laminates showed areas of poor bonding. The roll bonded laminates were found to have numerous surface blisters, which were easily identified visually. C-scan and metallographic analysis confirmed these unbonded areas occurred at the outside primary/secondary bondplanes. The explosive bonded laminate was found to be free of unbonded areas, as detectable by C-scan. The poor bonding behavior of the diffusion bonded panels was later evidenced when specimens were heat treated. It was found that approximately 20% of the heat treatment specimen blanks suffered delamination along 7475 Al/1100 Al interfaces due to the severity of the water quench following solution treatment. This delamination was most prevalent in the laminate blanks with the thinnest 1100 Al interleaf [laminate DA3 with the 0.05mm (0.002 in.) thick interleaf].

Table II. Fracture Toughness Values of Monolithic
7475 and 7075 Al Sheet and Plate

Alloy and Temper	Nominal Thickness		Specimen Type	Apparent Fracture Toughness, K_{app}		Critical Fracture Toughness, K_c	
	mm	(in.)		MPa \sqrt{m}	(ksi \sqrt{in})	MPa \sqrt{m}	(ksi \sqrt{in})
7475-T761 Al Sheet	2.3	(0.090)	SEN	64.8	(59.0)	85.5	(77.8)
				66.2	(60.2)	94.2	(85.7)
				64.0	(58.2)	90.6	(82.4)
				avg. 65.0	(59.1)	avg. 90.1	(82.0)
7475-T7651 Al Plate	11.9	(0.470)	SEN	60.1	(54.7)	66.5	(60.5)
				61.1	(55.6)	65.6	(59.7)
				59.9	(54.5)	66.8	(60.8)
				avg. 60.4	(54.9)	avg. 66.3	(60.3)
			CT	57.6	(52.4)	--	(--)
57.6	(52.4)	62.6	(57.0)				
57.9	(52.7)	67.6	(61.5)				
avg. 57.7	(52.5)	avg. 65.2	(59.2)				
7075-T76 Al Sheet	2.3	(0.090)	SEN	53.3	(48.5)	65.0	(59.1)
				50.7	(46.1)	63.7	(58.0)
				48.7	(44.3)	62.3	(56.7)
				avg. 50.9	(46.3)	avg. 63.7	(57.9)
7075-T7651 Al Plate	12.7	(0.500)	SEN	35.2	(32.0)	44.9	(40.9)
				34.6	(31.5)	40.7	(37.0)
				35.3	(32.1)	46.4	(42.2)
				avg. 35.0	(31.9)	avg. 44.0	(40.0)

The microstructures of all laminates were evaluated using optical metallography and electron probe microanalysis. Of principal interest was the primary/secondary alloy interface in each of the laminate systems. It was found that a discontinuous phase was often present at the primary/secondary interface for diffusion bonded and roll bonded laminates, as shown in Figure 1 for diffusion bonded 7475 Al/1100 Al. It is likely that this phase was an oxide. The explosive bonded laminate exhibited a smooth, well bonded interface with no additional metallurgical phases present at either the primary/secondary interface or at the center of the 7072 Al bondplane (corresponding to the joining plane between two 7075 Alclad sheets). The presence of an additional phase at the primary/secondary interface was found to be a significant factor in influencing the failure mechanisms in these laminates. In the diffusion bonded and roll bonded laminates where an interfacial phase was evident, there was a tendency for delamination to occur "adhesively" (i.e., separation occurred at the primary/secondary interface rather than within the soft secondary bondplane). Conversely, the explosive bonded laminate (which contained no interfacial phase) exhibited totally "cohesive" failure within the soft secondary metal interleaf.

Electron probe microanalysis was used to evaluate the amount of chemical diffusion across the secondary metal interleaf alloys for all six laminate configurations studied in this program. The diffusion gradients of Zn, Mg, and Cu were determined, since these were the three principal alloying elements in the primary laminae used in these laminates. It was found that substantial diffusion of these three elements had occurred from the primary alloy into the interleaf alloy (1100 Al or 7072 Al) for all laminates. This diffusion was a consequence of the heat treatments given each of the laminates. Typical diffusion profiles across an 1100 Al interleaf in the roll bonded 7475 Al/1100 Al laminate are shown in Figure 2. It was found that the interleaf thickness significantly affected the diffusion profiles. This is shown in Figure 3 for the diffusion of Zn from the primary 7475 Al into 1100 Al in diffusion bonded laminates DA3, DA1, and DA2. These laminates had 1100 Al interleaf thicknesses of 0.05mm (0.002 in.), 0.13mm (0.005 in.), and 0.25mm (0.010 in.), respectively. As is evident from Figure 3 it is possible that sufficient diffusion had occurred in laminate DA3 (0.05mm interleaf thickness) to make the interleaf hardenable by precipitation hardening heat treatments. A subsequent increase in strength in the interleaf alloy could cause the laminate to fail as a monolithic material rather than as separate layers as is required to achieve higher crack divider fracture toughness. Thus, the 0.05mm interleaf was deemed too thin for use in Al/Al laminates that must be subjected to precipitation hardening heat treatment.

Fracture Properties of Laminate Panels

Crack divider fracture toughness results on the diffusion bonded and roll bonded 7475 Al/1100 Al laminates are given in Table III. Similar results for the roll bonded and explosive bonded 7075 Al/7072 Al laminates are given in Table IV. (Tensile properties are given in Table A2 in the Appendix.) The majority of the fracture tests were conducted using single-edge-notched (SEN) specimens; however, additional compact tension (CT) specimen tests were performed on laminates DA1 and RA4. These additional tests were included to evaluate specimen geometry effects, since the compact tension configuration was to be used in subsequent fatigue crack growth studies on these materials. It can be seen from the SEN and CT fracture results for DA1 and RA4 that no significant differences in fracture properties were evident for tests completed with these two specimen types.

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 1. MICROGRAPHS OF DIFFUSION BONDED 7475 Al/1100 Al LAMINATE DAI SHOWING: (a) 1100 Al BONDPLANE AND (b) 7475 Al/1100 Al INTERFACE.

FIGURE 2. Zn, Mg, AND Cu DIFFUSION PROFILES ACROSS 0.13 mm (0.005 in.) 1100 Al INTERLEAF IN ROLL BONDED 7475 Al/1100 Al LAMINATE RA4.

FIGURE 3. COMPARISON OF Zn DIFFUSION PROFILES ACROSS 1100 Al INTERLEAVES OF DIFFERENT THICKNESSES IN 7475 Al/1100 Al DIFFUSION BONDED LAMINATES DA1, DA2, AND DA3.

In evaluating the fracture toughness of these laminates, conditional (K_Q), apparent (K_{app}), and critical (K_C) fracture toughness values were determined. It was found that these materials exhibited essentially plane stress failure in each of the primary layers constituting the laminate. Consequently, K_Q values were not appropriate indicators of the toughness of these materials. Rather, critical fracture toughness K_C was found to be the most meaningful measure of toughness, especially when comparing laminate properties with baseline monolithic sheet and plate metal. This method of comparison has been used by previous investigators (4, 6).

The plane stress failure behavior of the laminates was reflected in significantly higher K_C values than those for monolithic baseline alloys of the same thickness. Comparative toughness values for baseline sheet and plate metal and laminates are given in Table V (for 7475 Al primary alloy) and Table VI (for 7075 Al primary alloy). Several observations can be made from the comparisons shown in these tables. (1) The diffusion bonded 7475 Al/1100 Al laminates DA1, DA2 and DA3 had essentially the same fracture toughness, regardless of the secondary alloy interleaf thickness. (2) The diffusion bonded and roll bonded 7475 Al/1100 Al laminates possessed significantly

Table III. Fracture Toughness Values of
7475 Al/1100 Al Laminate Panels

Bonding Process	Panel Designation	1100 Al Interleaf Thickness		Specimen Type	Apparent Fracture Toughness, K_{app}		Critical Fracture Toughness, K_c		
		mm	(in.)		MPa \sqrt{m}	(ksi $\sqrt{in.}$)	MPa \sqrt{m}	(ksi $\sqrt{in.}$)	
Diffusion	DA1	0.13	(0.005)	SEN	64.4	(58.6)	97.8	(89.0)	
					67.1	(61.1)	105.7	(96.2)	
					69.2	(63.0)	106.4	(96.9)	
					avg. 66.9	(60.9)	avg. 103.3	(94.0)	
					CT	71.7	(65.2)	98.8	(89.9)
						73.9	(67.2)	100.1	(91.1)
					73.2	(66.6)	100.8	(91.7)	
					avg. 72.9	(66.3)	avg. 99.9	(90.9)	
	DA2	0.25	(0.010)	SEN	63.3	(57.6)	92.9	(84.5)	
					65.6	(59.7)	101.4	(92.3)	
					66.4	(60.4)	103.7	(94.4)	
					avg. 65.1	(59.2)	avg. 99.3	(90.4)	
	DA3	0.05	(0.002)	SEN	69.6	(63.3)	103.5	(94.2)	
Roll	RA4	0.13	(0.005)	SEN	63.5	(57.8)	88.4	(80.4)	
					65.0	(59.1)	88.1	(80.2)	
					65.0	(59.1)	88.0	(80.1)	
					avg. 64.5	(58.7)	avg. 88.2	(80.2)	
					CT	72.3	(65.8)	89.9	(81.8)
						71.5	(65.1)	88.7	(80.7)
					76.4	(69.5)	100.1	(91.1)	
					avg. 73.4	(66.8)	avg. 92.9	(84.5)	

Table IV. Fracture Toughness Values of
7075 Al/7072 Al Laminate Panels

Bonding Process	Panel Designation	7072 Al Interleaf Thickness		Specimen Type	Apparent Fracture Toughness, K_{app}		Critical Fracture Toughness, K_c	
		mm	(in.)		MPa \sqrt{m}	(ksi $\sqrt{in.}$)	MPa \sqrt{m}	(ksi $\sqrt{in.}$)
Roll	RA1	0.13	(0.005)	SEN	45.2	(41.1)	56.5	(51.4)
					46.5	(42.3)	57.5	(52.3)
					48.5	(44.1)	64.1	(58.3)
					avg. 46.7	(42.5)	avg. 59.4	(54.0)
Explosive	EA1	0.13	(0.005)	SEN	48.0	(43.7)	64.3	(58.5)
					50.0	(45.5)	69.9	(63.6)
					46.4	(42.2)	63.3	(57.6)
					avg. 48.1	(43.8)	avg. 65.8	(59.9)

Table V. Comparison of Average Critical Fracture Toughness Values of 7475-T761, -T7651 Al Sheet and Plate and 7475 Al/1100 Al Laminates

Material	1100 Al Interleaf Thickness		Critical Fracture Toughness, K_c		% Retention of Single Layer Sheet Toughness	% Increase Above Monolithic Plate Toughness
	mm	(in.)	MPa \sqrt{m}	(ksi \sqrt{in})		
2.3mm (0.090 in.) Sheet	--	--	90.1	(82.0)	--	--
11.9 mm (0.47 in.) Plate	--	--	66.3	(60.3)	--	--
Diffusion Bonded Laminates	0.05	(0.002)	103.5	(94.2)	115%	56%
	0.13	(0.005)	103.3	(94.0)	115%	56%
	0.25	(0.010)	99.3	(90.4)	110%	50%
Roll Bonded Laminate	0.13	(0.005)	88.2	(80.2)	98%	33%

* K_c values determined using single-edge-notched specimens.

Table VI. Comparison of Average Critical Fracture Toughness Values of 7075-T76, -T7651 Al Sheet and Plate and 7075 Al/7072 Al Laminates

Material	7072 Al Interleaf Thickness		Critical Fracture Toughness, K_c		% Retention of Single Layer Sheet Toughness	% Increase Above Monolithic Plate Toughness
	mm	(in.)	MPa \sqrt{m}	(ksi \sqrt{in})		
2.3mm (0.090 in.) Sheet	--	--	63.7	(57.9)	--	--
12.7mm (0.47 in.) Plate	--	--	44.0	(40.0)	--	--
Roll Bonded Laminate	0.13	(0.005)	59.4	(54.0)	93%	35%
Explosive Bonded Laminate	0.13	(0.005)	65.8	(59.9)	103%	50%

* K_c values determined using single-edge-notched fracture specimens.

higher K_{IC} values than monolithic 7475 Al of the same thickness. This improvement in K_{IC} ranged from 50% to 56% for the diffusion bonded laminates and was 33% for the roll bonded laminate. (3) The single layer 7475 Al sheet properties were retained in all 7475 based laminates. (4) The roll bonded and explosive bonded 7075 Al/7072 Al laminates exhibited basically the same improved toughness relative to baseline monolithic 7075 plate and sheet as was found for the 7475 based laminates. (5) 7475 based laminates possessed much higher fracture toughnesses than the 7075 based laminates.

An additional feature evident from Tables V and VI was that the amount of fracture toughness improvement obtained through lamination was not as pronounced for the roll bonded laminates as for the diffusion bonded and explosive bonded panels. This difference in fracture behavior is considered to be related to the inherent properties of the primary alloy laminae. The diffusion bonded and explosive bonded laminates were composed of primary laminae sheet that had been subsequently bonded together; whereas, the roll bonded primary layers were never rolled to sheet thickness prior to laminate bonding. Rather, in rolling subsections to form the laminate the laminae were more nearly being processed as a plate, and therefore, the laminae possessed plate-like properties, which have been shown to be generally inferior to sheet properties. Thus, the roll bonded laminates exhibited fracture toughness that was inferior to the diffusion and explosive bonded laminates because they possessed intrinsic plate properties in lieu of sheet properties. This same observation has been made previously by Almond, et al. (5).

FIGURE 4. COMPARISON OF LOAD/CLIP GAGE DISPLACEMENT FRACTURE TEST RESULTS FOR DIFFUSION BONDED 7475 Al/1100 Al LAMINATE DA1 AND MONOLITHIC 7475-T7651 Al PLATE.

As noted previously it was found that all laminate fracture specimens exhibited plane stress failure behavior of the individual primary layers. This plane stress failure behavior of the laminates contrasted sharply with the predominantly plane strain failure observed for the monolithic baseline 7475 Al and 7075 Al plate alloys. The plane stress failure of the individual primary layers is indicative of the much higher toughness values noted for these laminates. Similar failure surfaces in laminated panels have been noted in previous evaluations of laminate failures, and this type of failure mechanism is considered essential for obtaining high toughness in laminate materials. The difference in failure mode between laminate and monolithic material was reflected noticeably in the load/crack gage displacement fracture curves. An example is shown in Figure 4, where the curves for diffusion bonded 7475 Al/1100 Al laminate DA1 and monolithic 7475 Al plate are given. The specimens tested had similar initial crack lengths, but the laminated specimen sustained a maximum load approximately 25% higher than the monolithic plate specimen and a total crack extension prior to failure that was four times that of the monolithic plate specimen. K_C was $106 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ ($96.9 \text{ ksi}\sqrt{\text{in.}}$) for the laminate material compared to $66.5 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ ($60.5 \text{ ksi}\sqrt{\text{in.}}$) for the monolithic plate alloy.

FIGURE 5. FRACTOGRAPH OF DIFFUSION BONDED 7475 Al/1100 Al LAMINATE DA3 SEN SPECIMEN FAILURE SURFACE, SHOWING "ADHESIVE" DELAMINATION OF 1100 Al INTERLEAF FROM ADJACENT 7475 Al PRIMARY LAYERS.

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 6. FRACTOGRAPHS OF ROLL BONDED LAMINATES RA1 AND RA4 SEN SPECIMEN FAILURE SURFACES: (a) "COHESIVE" FAILURE IN 7072 Al INTERLEAF IN RA1; (b) "ADHESIVE" DELAMINATION AT 7475 Al/1100 Al INTERFACE IN RA4.

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 7. FRACTOGRAPHS OF 7075 Al/7072 Al ROLL BONDED (RA1) AND EXPLOSIVE BONDED (EA1) LAMINATES SEN SPECIMEN FAILURE SURFACES SHOWING DIMPLED RUPTURE ACROSS 7072 Al INTERLEAVES: (a) RA1; (b) EA1.

Fractography of failed fracture specimens was conducted using scanning electron fractography. Fractographs illustrating the various modes of failure in these laminates are given in Figures 5, 6 and 7. It was found that all diffusion bonded laminates exhibited "adhesive" delamination at the primary/secondary alloy interface, as shown in Figure 5. It was noted previously that all diffusion bonded 7475 Al/1100 Al failed at essentially the same toughness level, regardless of interleaf thickness. The "adhesive" nature of bondplane failure in these laminates precluded mechanical evaluation of interleaf thickness effects on the fracture toughness, since the interleaf strength level had no effect on the bondplane separation (delamination) strength.

In the roll bonded laminates it was found that both "adhesive" delamination and "cohesive" interleaf failure occurred, as illustrated in Figures 6 and 7. The mixed "adhesive", "cohesive" failure modes in the roll bonded laminates had no effect on development of plane stress failure shear lips in the primary layers in these laminates. The "cohesive" failure mode in the interleaf is preferable to "adhesive" failure, since the failure strength of the bondplane can then be controlled and predicted. If the failure is "adhesive" in nature, little control can be exercised over what strength the bondplane will fail, and premature or excessive delamination could result. The explosive bonded 7075 Al/7072 Al laminate exhibited 100% dimpled rupture across the 7072 Al interleaf and had very little tendency to separate completely in the bondplane, as shown in Figure 7. The low strength and high ductility of the 7072 Al interleaf material in this laminate allowed full development of plane stress shear lips in all primary 7075 Al layers. It was considered that this laminate failed in an "ideal" manner.

The improvement in crack divider fracture toughness that can be achieved through lamination is summarized schematically in Figure 8. Here it is shown that: (1) the toughness of a laminate depends ultimately on the plane stress toughness of the individual layers comprising the laminate, and (2) maximum toughness is achieved by selecting the primary layer thickness to correspond

FIGURE 8. EFFECT OF LAMINATION ON CRACK DIVIDER FRACTURE TOUGHNESS.

to that thickness at which the K_C vs. thickness curve for single layer metal reaches a peak. These conclusions are based on the important requirement that the primary layers in a laminate be bonded together in such a way that they fail individually under plane stress conditions. The key factor controlling plane stress failure of the primary layers is that failure occurs in the interleaf bondplane prior to development of a plane strain condition through the thickness of the laminate. This means that the interleaf bondplane strength must be somewhat lower than the primary metal strength. A higher ductility in the interleaf metal insures that excessive delamination does not occur.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were made from this experimental investigation:

1. Totally metallic, fracture resistant Al/Al laminates can be fabricated by diffusion, roll, and explosive bonding techniques.
2. All Al/Al laminate systems evaluated showed substantially higher fracture toughness in the crack divider orientation than corresponding monolithic plate alloys. Fracture toughness improvement through lamination ranged from 33% to 56%.
3. The primary alloy single layer sheet toughness was retained in all laminate systems. The average K_C values of the laminates were measured to be 88% to 115% of the K_C values for the single layer primary alloy sheets of equivalent thickness as the primary laminae.
4. The crack divider fracture toughness of a laminate depends ultimately on the plane stress toughness of the individual primary metal layers comprising the laminates. Therefore, maximum toughness is achieved through lamination by selecting the primary metal layer thickness to correspond to that thickness at which the K_C vs. thickness relation for that single layer metal is at a maximum.
5. The principal requirement for attaining high fracture toughness in laminates is that the primary metal layers in a laminate be bonded together in such a way that they fail individually under plane stress conditions. The key factor controlling plane stress failure of the primary layers is that failure occurs at the primary/secondary bond prior to development of a plane strain condition through the thickness of the laminate. In metal/metal laminates, this means that the interleaf metal strength must be less than the primary metal strength. A high ductility in the interleaf metal insures that excessive delamination does not occur.
6. Laminates having 7475 Al as the primary alloy were found to have considerably higher crack divider fracture toughness than similar laminates having 7075 Al as the primary alloy (an average of 63% for roll bonded laminates).

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Appendix

Table A1. Average Tensile Properties of Monolithic 7475 and 7075 Al Sheet and Plate

Alloy and Temper	Nominal Thickness		0.2% Yield Strength		Ultimate Strength		% Elongation
	mm	(in.)	MPa	(ksi)	MPa	(ksi)	
7475-T761 Al Sheet	2.3	(0.090)	468	(67.9)	514	(74.5)	13.1
7475-T7651 Al Plate	13.2	(0.520)	474	(68.8)	522	(75.7)	16.6
7075-T76 Al Sheet	2.3	(0.090)	479	(69.4)	538	(77.9)	12.0
7075-T7651 Al Plate	12.7	(0.500)	478	(69.3)	530	(76.8)	15.1

Table A2. Average Tensile Properties of 7475 Al/1100 Al and 7075 Al/7072 Al Laminate Panels

Panel Designation	Bonding Process	Primary/Secondary Alloys	0.2% Yield Strength		Ultimate Strength		% Elongation
			MPa	(ksi)	MPa	(ksi)	
DA1	Diffusion	7475 Al/ 1100 Al	456	(66.2)	502	(77.8)	12.5
DA2			442	(64.1)	487	(70.6)	12.4
DA3			470	(68.2)	518	(75.1)	11.8
RA4	Roll	7075 Al/ 7072 Al	460	(66.8)	521	(75.5)	15.4
RA1			471	(68.3)	536	(77.7)	13.3
EI	Explosive		472	(68.5)	525	(76.1)	14.9